

Internal Stakeholders' Knowledge and Attitude towards Inclusive Education

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the extent of knowledge and the level of attitude of the internal stakeholders towards inclusive education. The respondents of this study consisted of 5 school heads, 130 teachers, and 150 randomly selected students in the secondary schools in the district of Hinoba-an, Division of Negros Occidental. The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational method of research. She also used a validated researcher-made questionnaire for measuring knowledge and attitude of the internal stakeholders. The statistical tools used in

this study were weighted mean and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. The study revealed that the internal stakeholders have very high extent of knowledge towards inclusive education. The school heads and teachers have positive level of attitude while the students have a very positive level of attitude towards inclusive education in terms of their beliefs and feelings. In terms of actions, the level of attitude of the school heads and students is very positive while the teachers have a positive level of attitude. In addition, there is a strong relationship between the

internal stakeholders' extent of knowledge and their level of attitude towards inclusive education. Likewise, there is a strong relationship between the school heads' educational attainment and their (a) extent of knowledge and (b) level of attitude towards inclusive education.

Keywords: *inclusive education, internal stakeholders, knowledge, attitude*

Introduction

If the right to education for all is to become a reality, this must ensure that all learners have access to the culture of education that addresses the indispensable needs of the learners and improves the kind of life that they have, even those that have special needs too. Educational efforts were made by the government to include students with disabilities in inclusive education/general schools which promise better educational results for all children (Sakız and Wood, 2015).

The principle of equal educational opportunities which states that "all learners, whatever their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other condition" is being recognized in the Philippines, as a signatory of the Salamanca Statement of Action on Special Needs Education (Salamanca Statement, 1994). This program was brought up in the Philippines owing to the efforts of the Department of Education Culture and Sports (now DepEd) Order no. 26 which founded the inclusive education.

Likewise, inclusive education system is fundamental for realizing the rights of learning opportunities of the children with disabilities and not be excluded from the general school system on the ground of their disabilities. Ideally, it allows children with and without disabilities to attend the same classes in the general schools with addition of educational supports (Titrek et al., 2017). However, there is not enough knowledge of the relationship between what teachers think about the widespread adoption of policies on mainstreaming and on inclusive education for children and young people with special educational needs and the type of learning environments that they provide.

It has been distinguished that learners with special needs are not into a single homogeneous group. Each of them has personal needs and passes different road blocks. Their disabilities vary which may include categories such as visual, hearing, physical, albinism, and speech impairment. Others are related to gifted children, talented ones, or slow learners (Gathumbi, Ayot, Kimemia and Ondigi, 2015). It cannot be denied that many teachers, school administrators and parents are apprehensive about the outcomes of making children with special needs part of regular schools (Gathumbi et al., 2015). Nonetheless, there is no strong proof that would attest that teachers, school administrators and students possess the crucial attitude to facilitate the accommodation of the heterogeneous nature of the learners in inclusive education (Gathumbi et al., 2015).

Apparently, in the locality where the researcher is currently working, pupils with disabilities in the whole district are catered in one of the barangays near the district in a program that facilitates children with special needs with only three teachers. Unfortunately, those families that are poor cannot afford to send their children to that program due to its distance.

Hunt and McDonnell stated that teachers, students and administrators are the critical stakeholders in the movement to create inclusive schools (cited in Bebetos, Derri, Filippou, Zetou, & Vernadakis, 2014). In addition, in order to succeed in the goals of Education for All (EFA), the teachers and school administrators should act as a pivot around which the educational programs revolve.

It is important to address the non- acceptance attitude of Filipinos in inclusive education, teachers' readiness as to lack of trainings, and availability of materials or the lack of materials for children with a disability.

Hence, the researcher was prompted to conduct a study in the locality where she is currently working after sensing the need to further investigate the knowledge and attitude of administrators, teachers, and even students towards inclusive education.

This study will explore teachers, administrators and students' knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education.

Research Design

The research utilized the descriptive-correlational survey. It was descriptive because it would (a) evaluate the extent of knowledge and the level of attitude of the internal stakeholders towards inclusive education and (b) would identify the profile of the internal stakeholders. On the other hand, it was also correlational because the mentioned variables were correlated.

Research Environment

The place of the study is the Municipality of Hinoba-an, the last municipality in Negros Occidental which has 13 barangays. It is in the southern part of Negros Occidental and people earn their living through fishing and farming. Some have no access of electricity especially those parts of barangays located in the highland. Although other barangays have electricity, yet there are no internet connections.

The study focused specifically on the secondary schools in the District of Hinoba-an, Division of Negros Occidental. These schools are administered by three (3) principals and two (2) teachers in charge for extension and annexed school.

Research Respondents

The study utilized all school heads and teachers and 30 randomly selected students in sections with students with a disability in every secondary school in the District of Hinoba-an, Division of Negros Occidental.

Research Instruments

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire gained by the researcher through reading books, journals, and online references. The researcher also considered the use of Multidimensional Attitudes toward Inclusive Education Scale (MATIES) instrument (cited in Barnes & Gaines, 2015) to determine the level of attitude. The questionnaire consists of three parts; Part I deals with the profile of the respondents. Part II indicates the extent of knowledge of the internal stakeholders towards inclusive education. Part III involves the level of attitude of the internal stakeholder towards inclusive education. The survey item responses were rated on a five-point Likert's scale as follows: strongly agree, agree, moderately agree, disagree, and strongly disagree, scored 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Questions for the level of attitude were categorized into 3 domains: cognitive (beliefs), affective (feelings), and behavioural (actions). The researcher made three (3) different questionnaires for the school heads, teachers and students.

The researcher asked permission that instrument would be used in this study. The whole questionnaires were presented to three experts in the field of inclusive education for content validity and cross checking if the items were aligned with the specific problems of the study. Two of them are a DPS SPED teacher and a SPET 1 and the other one is a Doctor of Education, an EPS- LRMDS SDO and a former Division SPED coordinator at Bayawan City Division, Bayawan City. These three experts validated all parts of the questionnaire. All suggestions from the three experts were taken into consideration in the final construction.

To ensure item reliability, a dry-run was made. There were 30 selected elementary teachers and 30 secondary students who served as the respondents. These teachers and students were not the actual respondents. The items were tested for its reliability using the Cronbach's alpha test. According to McMillan and Schumacher, this test was regarded as the most suitable type for survey research where items were not scored right or wrong and where each item could have different answers (cited in Feril, 2014). This was calculated to verify the internal consistency reliability of the items. It is a measure of the extent to which all the variables in the scale are positively related to each other and its theoretical value varies from 0 to 1. Higher values of alpha are more desirable and a value of 0.70 is considered acceptable. The reliability coefficient yielded a value of 0.939, 0.779, 0.842, and 0.833 for the level of knowledge and the level of attitude with the three domains namely cognitive, affective and behavioral of the teachers and a value of 0.810, 0.750, 0.746, and 0.751 for the students on the same areas, respectively. This means that the items were reliable. Then the final revision of the questionnaires was done.

Research Procedure

After the design hearing, the researcher incorporated all the suggestions and corrections of the members of the panel. A letter of request was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Negros Occidental to ask permission to conduct the study. Upon the endorsement of the Dean of the Graduate School Foundation University, the signed and approved request was presented to the district supervisor and principals of the secondary schools. The researcher explained the purpose of the conduct of the study and they were assured of the confidentiality of the study.

The retrieval of the questionnaires was done a week after for the school heads and teachers but for the students it was done right after the respondents answered the questions. Then, results were tabulated and tallied using the MS Excel, analyzed and interpreted.

Findings

Table 1. Extent of Knowledge of the School Heads and Teachers on Inclusive Education

	Indicators N= 135	School Heads		Teachers	
		w \bar{x}	VD	w \bar{x}	VD
1.	Inclusive education is a placement of all students including children with disabilities in mainstream classrooms with the necessary support given within these classrooms.	4.40	SA	4.25	SA
2.	Inclusive education is when an educational environment is given the same level of scrutiny as the child in order to assess the adaptations needed to achieve a more effective match between the child's educational needs and the instruction offered.	3.60	A	4.20	A
3.	Inclusive education is an approach which aims to develop a child-focus within schools by acknowledging that all children are individuals with different learning needs and speeds.	5.00	SA	4.48	SA
4.	Inclusive education is considered to be a means of providing educational opportunities for all children, including children with disabilities.	4.60	SA	4.44	SA
5.	Inclusive education is a way of reducing social discrimination.	4.20	A	4.40	SA
6.	Inclusive education works as a catalyst for change because it does not only enhance education within schools, but also represents an increased awareness of human rights and leads to a reduction in social discrimination.	4.80	SA	4.35	SA
7.	Inclusive education enhances social interaction and inclusion among students and reduces negative stereotypes towards special needs children.	4.40	SA	4.29	SA
8.	Inclusive education is seen as a system which caters for the needs of a diverse range of learners and supports diversity, effectively eliminating all forms of discrimination.	4.60	SA	4.28	SA
9.	Inclusion has the potential to be a very effective starting point for addressing the Rights of the Child in a range of cultures and contexts.	4.20	A	4.26	SA
10.	Inclusive education is a development keeping children with disabilities in mainstream education settings rather than referring them to special schools.	3.80	A	3.95	A
11.	Inclusive education is defined as the education of children with disabilities with their non-disabled peers to the maximum extent appropriate.	4.40	SA	4.02	A
12.	In an inclusive education system, school and school practices were developed to support a diverse range of learners in mainstream settings which made schools more flexible and child-centered.	4.40	SA	4.31	SA
Composite		4.37	VH	4.27	VH

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Knowledge
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 1 indicates the extent of knowledge of the school heads and the teachers on inclusive education. As revealed, school heads and teachers generally show very high extent of knowledge as evidenced by the composite $w\bar{x}$ of 4.37 and 4.27, respectively. It implies that they have enough understanding on what inclusive education means and the opportunity that it brings on the lives of every learner with disability. As noted by Greenfield et al (2010), vital to the implementation and success of a school- wide instructional reform initiative is assessing the

perceptions of educators. With school heads and teachers acquiring deeper understanding on the rationale of the program, they can design the environment and classes in ways that help children learn and achieve to their fullest potential. On the other hand, the findings also imply that both school heads and teachers have high extent of knowledge only on inclusive education as a development of keeping children with disabilities in mainstream education settings rather than referring them to special schools and a more effective match between the child's educational needs and the instruction offered. In the same way, Roden et al (2013) found out that many public schools' principals and teachers displayed moderate extent of knowledge on the inclusive education program. This is due to many state governments which began to establish laws ensuring a free and appropriate education for all students. Furthermore, the study of Pingle, Sudha & Garg, Indu. (2015) on the Effect of Inclusive Education Awareness Program on Pre-service Teachers, revealed that pre-service teachers from experimental group have gained awareness about inclusive education to a moderate extent.

Table 2. Extent of Knowledge of the Students on Inclusive Education

Indicators n=150	w \bar{x}	VD	
1. Inclusive education is a placement of all students including children with disabilities in mainstream classrooms with the necessary support given within these classrooms.	4.45	SA	
2. Inclusive education is when an educational environment is given the same level of scrutiny as the child in order to assess the adaptations needed to achieve a more effective match between the child's educational needs and the instruction offered.	4.31	SA	
3. Inclusive education is an approach which aims to develop a child-focus within schools by acknowledging that all children are individuals with different learning needs and speeds.	4.58	SA	
4. Inclusive education is considered to be a means of providing educational opportunities for all children, including children with disabilities.	4.66	SA	
5. Inclusive education is a way of reducing social discrimination.	4.11	A	
6. Inclusive education works as a catalyst for change because it does not only enhance education within schools, but also represents an increased awareness of human rights and leads to a reduction in social discrimination.	4.49	SA	
7. Inclusive education enhances social interaction and inclusion among students and reduces negative stereotypes towards special needs children.	3.88	A	
8. Inclusive education is seen as a system which caters for the needs of a diverse range of learners and supports diversity, effectively eliminating all forms of discrimination.	3.81	A	
9. Inclusion has the potential to be a very effective starting point for addressing the Rights of the Child in a range of cultures and contexts.	4.53	SA	
10. Inclusive education is a development keeping children with disabilities in mainstream education settings rather than referring them to special schools.	4.37	SA	
11. Inclusive education is defined as the education of children with disabilities with their non-disabled peers to the maximum extent appropriate.	4.23	SA	
12. In an inclusive education system, school and school practices were developed to support a diverse range of learners in mainstream settings which made schools more flexible and child-centered.	4.45	SA	
Composite	4.32	VH	
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Knowledge
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2 reveals that generally, students have a very high extent of knowledge towards inclusive education as evidenced by the composite $w\bar{x}$ of 4.32. It only shows that not only the school heads and teachers are highly aware about what inclusive education is, but also the students. This may signify that less problem will occur between students with and without disabilities during classroom activities.

This further implies that regular students gaining knowledge on the objectives and importance of inclusive education, they can easily adjust to the situation and their academic performance will not be at stake. This is affirmed by York et al., who found out that inclusive education does not reduce the academic progress of non-disabled children and that presence of students with a disability does not affect attention and time given to non-disabled children. Non-disabled children do not necessarily learn undesirable behavior from children with disabilities. In addition to that, studies prove that placement in inclusive classrooms does not interfere with the academic performance of students without disabilities with respect to the amount of allocated time and engaged instructional time (cited in Whitbread, 2014).

Nevertheless, students' understanding on inclusive education as a way of effectively eliminating all forms of discrimination, enhances social interaction system which caters for the needs of a diverse range of learners, and supports diversity falls into high extent only. This finding is similar to the study of Gafoor and Asaraf (2009) which revealed that there is an increase of the extent of knowledge of students regarding inclusive education program in India and classified as moderate extent only.

Table 3. Level of Attitude of the School Heads on Inclusive Education in Terms of Beliefs

Indicators N= 5	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description n	Level of Attitude
1. I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.	4.80	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I believe that students with a disability can be taught in a regular classroom setting.	4.60	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior among all students.	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I believe that all students can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.	4.20	Agree	Positive
5. I believe that students with a disability should not be in special education schools so that they can socialize with regular students	4.20	Agree	Positive
6. I believe that students with a disability should be segregated because it is too expensive to modify the physical environment of the school.	3.00	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	4.20	Agree	Positive

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative

Table 3 reflects a positive level of attitude of the school heads towards inclusive education in terms of their beliefs as evidenced by the composite $w\bar{x}$ of 4.20. School heads believed the importance of curriculum adaptation to meet the individual needs of all students with or without a disability and that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior among all students. They also believed that students with disability should be catered in a regular classroom setting. In like manner, the study of Khochen & Radford (2012) on “The Attitudes of Head Teachers towards Inclusion in Lebanon”, indicated the positive attitudes towards the inclusion of students in mainstream schools. However, they further revealed that school heads expressed reservations about including all students, especially those with social, emotional, and behavioral difficulties.

On the other hand, the physical environment of the school and the materials needed should be considered. The school heads’ level of attitude in terms of belief on this area is of moderate level ($w\bar{x} = 3.00$). Gathumbi et al(2015) revealed in their study that physical infrastructure and instructional resources are unsuitable to support learners with special needs. Thus, school heads should have access and good rapport to the community where they can ask assistance to provide resources to help learners with special needs.

Table 4. Level of Attitude of the Teachers on Inclusive Education in Terms of Beliefs

Indicators N= 130	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I believe that all students can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.	4.38	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I believe that students with a disability can be taught in a regular classroom setting.	4.36	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.	4.35	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior among all students.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
5. I believe that students with a disability should not be in special education schools so that they can socialize with regular students.	3.93	Agree	Positive
6. I believe that students with a disability should be segregated because it is too expensive to modify the physical environment of the school.	3.56	Agree	Positive
Composite	4.14	Agree	Positive
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative	

Table 4 presents that generally, teachers have positive level of attitude ($w\bar{x} = 4.14$) in terms of beliefs towards inclusive education. Like the school heads as shown in Table 3, teachers also regard that students with special needs can be taught in a regular classroom and this is supported by the findings of Dapudong (2014). In her study, teachers believed that students with special educational needs should have equal opportunities to participate in all school sponsored age-appropriate activities and general education. Teachers also believed that inclusive education can be possible if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs. The results adhere to the study of Lombardi and Murray (2010) on faculty members’ attitudes and beliefs regarding disability and disability laws. Results indicated more positive

attitudes toward providing accommodations and implementing inclusive education. Faculty responses also revealed that faculty in the department of education reported greater fairness in providing accommodations and greater knowledge of disability law. Furthermore, they strongly believe that students with a disability can learn more in a regular curriculum together with the regular students. Moreover, Andaya et al (2015) revealed that regular teachers believed that inclusion is possible through the help of the school physician, medical personnel and guidance counselor and they constantly coordinate and consult stakeholders to ensure a comprehensive understanding of its objectives, activities, and programs of inclusive education.

Similarly, teachers believed that inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability. Furthermore, Pearson et al. (2003) used interviews to examine teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education (n = 224). Many teachers agreed with the two positive values of inclusion, namely 'realization of equal opportunity' (75.9%) and 'a good chance for students to interact' (75.5%), whereas 61.8% responded positively to the item that 'inclusion is an educational value to other students.

On the contrary, Fuchs (2010) indicated that teachers feel overburdened by the demands and responsibilities of teaching in an inclusion classroom and not have a positive attitude about it. In the same manner, the study of Gary revealed that many regular education teachers who feel unprepared and fearful to teach students with disabilities in regular classes displayed frustration, anger, and negative attitude toward inclusive education (cited in Dapudong, 2014). Their focus was on the challenges posed by students with special needs, and on need to have extra, but unavailable, assistance in the classroom. Regular teachers generally believed that students with special needs are not their responsibility, but that of the special education teacher. This is also true in the study of Valeo (2008), which stated that the overall attitudes of regular teachers with regard to placing students with special needs in regular classrooms were negative.

Table 5. Level of Attitude of the Students on Inclusive Education in Terms of Beliefs

Indicators n= 150	w \bar{x}	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.	4.77	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I believe that all students can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.	4.69	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior among all students.	4.49	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I believe that students with disability should be taught in a regular classroom setting.	4.45	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
5. I believe that students with disability should be included with other students in a regular class.	4.05	Agree	Positive
6. I believe that students with disability should not be in special education schools so that they can experience acceptance in the regular school.	3.81	Agree	Positive
Composite	4.38	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative	

The above table depicts the very positive attitude ($w\bar{x} = 4.38$) of the students on inclusive education in terms of beliefs. Students expressed that students with a disability should be taught in a regular class and that they wanted to have classmates with a disability in a regular classroom setting so that they can experience acceptance in the regular school. It shows that these regular students believed that learning is still possible or even enjoyable having a classmate with disability. Dapudong (2014) acknowledged that placing children with physical, behavioral or academic difficulties together with regular children in mainstream classrooms is a way of reducing social discrimination. This can be possible only if the regular students are willing to adjust and it is worth noting that the students of the current study show a positive view about the said inclusion. Furthermore, research demonstrates that students with very positive attitude in dealing person with a disability in the classroom, also shows a very high and positive beliefs on the abilities of students with a disability. They further agree that students with a disability should be treated equally with the regular students (Akiba, 2011). However, findings of Qi and Ha (2012) revealed that children without disabilities wanted peers with disabilities to participate in their physical education classes but they did not want them as teammates.

Table 6. Level of Attitude of the School Heads on Inclusive Education in Terms of Feelings

Indicators N = 5	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I am pleased when my teachers are able to understand students with a disability.	5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I am contented when my teachers reported that they can communicate well with students with a disability.	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I am happy to tell my teachers to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students.	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I am happy when students with a disability can keep up with the day-to-day activity.	4.00	Agree	Positive
5. I am comfortable including students with a disability in a regular classroom with other students without a disability.	4.00	Agree	Positive
6. I am glad that students with a disability are included in the regular classroom, regardless of the severity of the disability.	3.40	Agree	Positive
Composite	4.20	Agree	Positive

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative

Table 6 reveals a positive level of attitude ($w\bar{x} = 4.20$) of school heads towards inclusive education in terms of feelings. Thus, administrators continue to enrich the curriculum, instructional materials and teachers through in-service training, cooperative planning and monitoring of activities. Some schools according to Andaya et al (2015) link with government officials and non-government officials for their social, moral and financial support and provide incentives to regular students. There is a need to develop knowledge based on inclusive education, to meet learning needs of individual students. Gathumbi et al (2015) stated that

there was a high concern about training of teachers for inclusion suggesting that training of teachers to include children with disabilities is a major concern.

School heads also revealed a positive level of attitude only on their feelings as students with a disability can keep up with the day-to-day activity inside the classroom. This result conforms to the recent studies of Chandler, (2015); Hack,(2014); Galano, (2012); Waller, (2012); Vazquez, (2010); who examined school administrators' attitudes and feelings on how they reviewed the importance of children with disabilities and their inclusion in the general schools. Their findings reported that the majority of the school administrators perceived favorable attitudes toward inclusion. Based on the academic and social benefits that children with disabilities can get from inclusion, the school administrators showed understanding that there is a need of integrating these children in order to make non-disabled children to be familiar with the children with disabilities. Furthermore, some of the studies found out that professional development through in- service training in special education were the key factor for the school. Thus, showing positive feelings by commending and supporting the efforts of the teachers in adjusting their own comfort just to cater to students with disability in a regular class is a key factor for positive inclusion.

Table 7. Level of Attitude of the Teachers on Inclusive Education in Terms of Feelings

Indicators N= 130	w \bar{x}	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I am pleased when I am able to understand students with a disability.	4.51	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I am happy when student with a disability can keep up with the day-to-day activity.	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I am contented when I can communicate well with students with a disability.	4.22	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I am agreeable to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students.	4.03	Agree	Positive
5. I am comfortable including students with a disability in a regular classroom with other students without a disability.	3.68	Agree	Positive
6. I am happy that students with a disability are included in the regular classroom, regardless of the severity of the disability.	3.57	Agree	Positive
Composite	4.07	Agree	Positive

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative

Table 7 shows a positive level of attitudes ($w\bar{x} = 4.07$) of teachers towards inclusive education in terms of feelings. Teachers are generally happy to have students with a disability. Thus, they feel happy if students with disability can keep up with the day-to-day activity and agreeable to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs. This finding corroborates with that of Dapudong's (2014) wherein respondents displayed positive response towards inclusive education. This finding is also similar to the study of Andaya et al (2015). They revealed that regular teachers show positive response to the enrolment of children with disabilities and treat them equally. They enrich the program by monitoring, modifying and updating the curriculum and instructional materials with consultations.

Bussing et al (2002) assessed teachers' confidence to educate pupils with AD/HD (n = 365). Teachers rated their confidence on their ability to perform a task on a five point Likerts' scale, ranging from 1 ('no confidence') to 5 ('strongly confident'). Teachers had to indicate their degree of confidence based on 10 statements such as 'I'm able to manage the stress caused by students with AD/HD in my classroom'. The mean score of 3.87 (SD = 0.95) indicates that teachers were fairly confident about their ability to educate pupils with AD/HD. Feelings of confidence by teachers were also investigated by Sadler (2005). This study showed that none of the participating teachers (n = 89) reported to be very confident in teaching children with speech and language difficulties.

Table 8. Level of Attitude of the Students on Inclusive Education in Terms of Feelings

Indicators n= 150	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I am glad that my classmates with disability are included in the regular classroom.	4.61	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I am happy when my classmate with disability can keep up with the day-to-day activities in our classroom.	4.53	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I am pleased when I am able to understand my classmate with disability.	4.48	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I am contented when I can communicate well with my classmates with disability.	4.46	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
5. I am comfortable if I have a classmate with disability.	3.93	Agree	Positive
Composite	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very Positive

Legend: Scale 4.21 – 5.00 3.41 – 4.20 2.61 – 3.40 1.81 – 2.60 1.00 – 1.80	Verbal Description Strongly Agree Agree Moderately Agree Disagree Strongly Disagree	Level of Attitude Very Positive Positive Moderately Positive Negative Very Negative
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Table 8 presents the students' level of attitude towards inclusive education in terms of feelings. As reflected in the table, students manifest a very positive level of attitude ($w\bar{x} = 4.07$). It shows how comfortable and contented they are in having a classmate with a disability. Identically, students are pleased that they can understand their classmate with a disability. This is also true to the study of Bebetos (2017) who revealed that majority of non-disabled students developed very positive attitudes towards the prospect of integrating pupils. This is due to the experiential knowledge, to the educational approach with modern audiovisual media as well as to the activities of cooperation and interdependence. It is also due to the simplicity of activities that contributed to the absence of obvious differences in performance among pupils with and without disabilities.

Table 9. Level of Attitude of the School Heads on Inclusive Education in Terms of Actions

Indicators N=5	w \bar{x}	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I am willing to send my teachers on training in teaching students with special needs.	5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I am willing to support learners with special needs through preparing the physical infrastructure and instructional resources with the collaboration from community and the MOOE.	4.80	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I am willing to adapt the assessment of individual students in order for the inclusive education to take place.	4.80	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I am willing to modify the physical environment to include students with a disability in the regular classroom.	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
5. I am willing to physically include students with a disability in the regular classroom with the necessary support.	4.20	Agree	Positive
6. I am willing to encourage students with a disability to participate in all social activities in the regular classroom.	4.00	Agree	Positive
Composite	4.53	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative	

Table 9 shows that school heads' level of attitude towards inclusive education in terms of actions is very positive ($w\bar{x} = 4.07$). Thus, school heads are willing to send their teachers on trainings and seminars related to special education program. Trainings for teachers are very important especially on instructional strategies. Slavin et al recognized the benefits of these strategies to all learners. These strategies are peer tutoring, cooperative learning groups, and differentiated instruction. Further, Slavin et al revealed that peer tutoring results in significant increase in spelling, social studies and other academic areas for students with and without a disability (cited in Whitbread, 2014). As a matter of fact, Katz (2012) found out that school principal's level of preparedness on inclusive education is high. Thus, Manitoba administrators sent their teachers for trainings, they provided scholarships for students with a disability and allotted budget for the instructional materials needed.

On the other note, Gathumbi et al (2015) revealed that there was a general lack of teacher trainings on pedagogy and knowledge on how to handle students with special needs. Likewise, the majority of the teachers lamented about the inadequacy of teaching aids for learners with special needs.

Although implementation of inclusive practices will be left to individual teachers in their own classrooms, the responsibility for making inclusion work is ultimately that of the principal (Young, 2010). The study also implies that school heads are willing to support learners with special needs through preparing the physical infrastructure and instructional resources with the collaboration from community and the MOOE. Likewise, the way that principals can support inclusive practice may include the way they use systems and structures that fall under their control (Katz, 2012a). In addition, research has indicated that the instructional leadership (Leithwood & Riehl, 2005) of a principal may play a crucial part in implementing inclusive school reform. Research into the influence principals have on implementing inclusive education points to the understanding that it is their beliefs, values and commitment that are the foundation of inclusive schools (Theoharis & Causton-Theoharis, 2008).

Table 10. Level of Attitude of the Teachers on Inclusive Education in Terms of Actions

Indicators N= 130	w \bar{x}	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I am willing to encourage students with a disability to participate in all social activities in the regular classroom.	4.24	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I am willing to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students regardless of their disability.	4.13	Agree	Positive
3. I am willing to adapt the assessment of individual students in order for the inclusive education to take place.	4.06	Agree	Positive
4. I am willing to adapt my communication techniques to ensure that all students with an emotional and behavioral disorder can be successfully included in the regular classroom	4.01	Agree	Positive
5. I am willing to modify the physical environment to include students with a disability in the regular classroom.	3.78	Agree	Positive
6. I am willing to physically include students with disability in the regular classroom with the necessary support.	3.65	Agree	Positive
Composite	3.98	Agree	Positive
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative

Table 10 connotes that teachers have positive level of attitude ($w\bar{x} = 3.98$) towards inclusive education in terms of actions. It implies that teachers are willing to include students with a disability in a regular classroom, to adapt their communication techniques, to adapt the assessment of individual students, and to modify the physical environment. The willingness of the teachers is a good indication that they are open to changes and will surely welcome intensive training on teaching children with special needs in an inclusive setting. This finding runs parallel with that of Dapudong 's study (2014) wherein teachers also agree that students with special needs should be welcomed in regular classes and students with special educational needs are given every opportunity to function in regular classrooms when possible.

Table 11. Level of Attitude of the Students on Inclusive Education in Terms of Actions

Indicators n= 150	w \bar{x}	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
1. I will help to modify the physical classroom environment to accommodate the needs of my classmate with a disability.	4.35	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. I will encourage my classmate with a disability to participate in all classroom activities.	4.29	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I will help my classmate with a disability in academic areas if the need arises and with the necessary support.	4.29	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. I will use communication techniques which can be easily understood by my classmates with a disability in the classroom.	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
Composite	4.30	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Level of Attitude
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately Positive
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Negative

Table 11 illustrates a very positive attitude ($w\bar{x} = 4.30$) of students in terms of actions towards inclusive education. Students confided through their responses that they are helpful and a good motivator individuals. It shows that not only they are willing to help to modify the physical classroom environment, but also in academic areas. Thus, they are willing to encourage their classmates with a disability to participate in all classroom activities. This is the attitude that students with disability need from their peers for them to feel that they really belong to the group. However, De Boer et al (2012) stressed that generally students hold neutral attitudes towards peers with disabilities because of the several variables especially the experience and knowledge they have about disabilities.

Moreover, the results indicate that attitudes and acceptance of peers relate to the social participation of students with disabilities. Implications of the findings are discussed in terms of promoting positive attitudes and acceptance of peers. Further, regular students showed concerns with their classmates with a disability by helping them in group presentations, including them in some socializations, and in other academic requirements.

Table 12. Relationship between the Extent of Knowledge and the Level of Attitude of the Internal Stakeholders towards Inclusive Education

Stakeholders	Computed r_s	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision	Remark
N= 135 and n= 150					
School Heads	0.975	Strong	_____	_____	_____
Teachers	0.557	Strong	_____	_____	_____
Students	0.562	Strong	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
	Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
	Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
	Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
	Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

The data in Table 12 indicate that there is a strong positive relationship ($r_s = 0.975$) between the school heads' extent of knowledge and their level of attitude towards inclusive education. This means that their knowledge on inclusive education is a determinant of their attitude towards its implementation. This also implies that school heads with higher knowledge on inclusive education tend to have better attitude on it. This finding is the same as the study of Ngwokabuenui (2013) which revealed that special education law knowledge has an overall significant effect on principals' attitudes toward inclusion. As such they can help educational administration programs in the preparation process of school principals in developing stronger, more positive attitudes toward inclusion as they prepare for the important role of director of school programming. As noted by Ugwu and Onukwufor (2018), high percentage of school heads had positive attitude towards inclusion. Principals with adequate knowledge of special education showed high positive attitude towards inclusion than those with limited knowledge.

On the other hand, the same degree of relationship ($r_s = 0.557$) is apparent between the teachers' extent of knowledge and their level of attitude towards inclusive education. This connotes that their knowledge is a predictor of their attitude towards the implementation of inclusive education. This further implies that the higher the knowledge of the teachers about inclusive education, the more positive also is their attitude towards it. The finding runs parallel with the study of Sharma and Chow (2012). They indicated that as teachers' knowledge increases after completing a course in inclusive education, their attitude becomes more positive. Thus, training in inclusion is an important factor in the formation of more positive attitudes towards inclusive practice and higher levels of self-efficacy among teachers.

Moreover, the data reveal that there is a strong relationship ($r_s = 0.562$) between the students' extent of knowledge and their level of attitude towards inclusive education. Since the students are randomly selected, the results are significantly tested. It shows that the computed p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that the relationship is significant. This also implies that students with higher knowledge on inclusive education are more likely to manifest better attitude towards it. This finding is similar to that of Cairns et al (2013). They found out that children from the more inclusive school had a greater number of prior experiences on children with disabilities and had more positive attitudes towards having pupils with disabilities in their own class. To conclude, these findings suggest that inclusion in schools may lead to a positive effect on children's acceptance and understanding of disabilities.

Table 13. Relationship between the School Heads' Extent of Knowledge and the Level of Attitude towards Inclusive Education and Their Profile

School heads... N= 5	Computed r_s	Degree of Relationship
Extent of Knowledge and Educational Attainment	0.527	Strong
Experience in Handling a School with Children with Disabilities	0.154	Weak
Level of Attitude and Educational Attainment	0.433	Moderate
Experience in Handling a School with Children with Disabilities	0.263	Weak

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
	Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
	Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
	Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
	Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

The data in Table 13 reflect that there is a strong relationship ($r_s = 0.527$) between the school heads' educational attainment and their extent of knowledge on inclusive education. This means that the more educated the school heads are, the higher their knowledge is towards it. This finding contradicts the study of LeMay (2017) which revealed that education level did not play a significant role in the knowledge and attitudes of administrators. However, participants' role and years of experience did play a significant role toward inclusion.

On the other hand, there is a moderate relationship ($r_s = 0.433$) between the school heads' educational attainment and their level of attitude towards inclusive education. This implies that their educational attainment is a predictor of their attitude towards it. The study of Titrek and Nguluma (2017) emphasized on the professional development through ongoing training related to the special education. This is due to the fact that ongoing training is one of the greatest factors in the formation of favorable attitudes among the school administrators toward inclusive education; and it is considered as a way of overcoming their lack of confidence while working with the children with disabilities.

The data show that the school heads' experience in handling a school with children with disabilities have a weak relationship with their knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. This finding contradicts that of Titrek's and Nguluma's (2017) which revealed that administrators' experience with the people with disabilities demonstrated significant impact to their attitudes toward the inclusion of children with disabilities.

Table 14. Relationship between the Teachers' Extent of Knowledge and the Level of Attitude towards Inclusive Education and Their Profile

Teachers... N= 130	Comp. r_s	Degree of Relationship
Teachers' Extent of Knowledge and...		
Educational Attainment	0.075	Very Weak
Years of Teaching Experience	0.005	Very Weak
Experience in Teaching Students with Disabilities	0.065	Very Weak
Teachers' Level of Attitude and...		
Educational Attainment	0.055	Very Weak
Years of Teaching Experience	0.006	Very Weak
Experience in Teaching Students with Disabilities	0.001	Very Weak

Legend:

Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

The data indicate that the profile of the teachers has a very weak relationship with their knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. This means that their educational attainment, years of teaching experience and experience in teaching students with disabilities are not considered as indicators of their knowledge and attitude. This finding is similar to that of Dapudong's (2014) wherein no significant difference in the attitudes of school teachers is revealed when they were grouped according to their degree held in terms of beliefs, feelings and actions.

The data also reflect that the teachers' level of attitude towards inclusive education and their years of teaching experience had a very weak relationship. This implies that teachers with either shorter or longer period of teaching experience obtain more or less same level of attitude. This finding is in contrast to the study of Gal et al (2010) who reported that teachers with fewer years of teaching experience held more positive attitudes towards inclusive education. Likewise, Topping and Jindal-Snape (2013) in a study of teaching and management staff in Scotland concluded that length of service was not a significant factor in attitude towards inclusion.

However, in the case of Thai teachers, the previous study revealed that those Thai teachers who have 6-10 years of teaching experience have more favorable attitude than those teachers with below six years of teaching experience.

In addition, teachers without experience in teaching children with special education needs were more negative in their beliefs regarding core perspectives of inclusion possibly because they lacked knowledge and specific skills in instructional and management skills than teachers with relevant experience (Gal et al., 2010).

Table 15. Relationship between the Students' Extent of Knowledge and the Level of Attitude towards Inclusive Education and Their Sex

Students... n= 150	Comp. r_{pbi}	p-value	Decision	Remark
Students' Extent of Knowledge and Their Sex	0.113	0.170	Do not reject H_0	Not significant
Students' Level of Attitude and Their Sex	0.159	0.053	Do not reject H_0	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend:

Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

The data in Table 15 show that the computed p-values (0.170 and 0.053) are all greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will not allow rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant relationship between the sex of the students and their knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. This may connote that male and female have more or less the same knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. This finding is similar to the study of Bebetos et al (2014) which revealed that both boys and girls showed more positive modified behavior on collaborating with a schoolmate with a disability in the physical education lesson.

On the other hand, this finding contradicts the study of Kalyvas et al (2011) which pointed out that girls are more responsible toward individuals with disabilities than boys. These findings are also in accordance with the results of Panagiotou et al (2008) which revealed that among personal characteristics, the most common determinant of children's attitudes towards peers with disabilities is sex, with females generally showing more positive attitudes than males.

Conclusions

Based on the findings cited above, the following conclusions are hereby drawn:

The internal stakeholders have very high extent of knowledge towards inclusive education.

1. The school heads and the teachers have positive level of attitude while the students have a very positive level of attitude towards inclusive education in terms of their beliefs and feelings. In terms of actions, the level of attitude of the school heads and the students is very positive while the teachers have a positive level of attitude.
3. There is a strong relationship between the internal stakeholders' extent of knowledge and their level of attitude towards inclusive education.
4. There is a strong relationship between the school heads' educational attainment and their (a) extent of knowledge and (b) level of attitude towards inclusive education.
5. There is a very weak relationship between the teachers' profile and their (a) knowledge and (b) attitude towards inclusive education.
6. There is no significant relationship between the sex of the students and their (a) knowledge and (b) attitude towards inclusive education.

In general, the internal stakeholders' knowledge is very high and their attitude towards inclusive education is positive.

Recommendations

On the bases of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following measures are recommended:

1. The Department of Education (DepEd) should make a follow-up seminars and trainings for school heads and teachers on inclusive education and this should be part of the in-service trainings of the division to upgrade their knowledge and maintain their positive attitude towards inclusive education.
2. DepEd with the school faculty should prepare an information-drive on inclusive education for students and be part of the yearly activity of the school in order to enhance students' knowledge and sustain their positive attitude.
3. DepEd with the school heads should prioritize the appropriate school facilities, equipment and should customize instructional materials in the MOOE to aid teachers in their classroom discussion.
4. Finally, a training matrix should be recommended for implementation to enhance the internal stakeholders' knowledge and the attitude towards inclusive education.

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Appendix

Survey Instrument

Internal Stakeholders' Knowledge and Attitude towards Inclusive Education

This questionnaire aims to identify internal stakeholders' knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. Kindly and honestly answer the following questions. It is assured that the information you share is confidential. Thank you very much for your time and cooperation.

Part I:

School: _____

- Educational Attainment: Bachelor's Degree
 With MA units
 Master's Degree
 With EDD/PhD Units
 Doctor's Degree

Number of Years of Experience in Handling a School with Children with Special Needs:
 ____year/years

Part II:

- Direction:
 1. Read each statement. Please respond as truthfully as you can.
 2. Place a check mark (√) on the column of your choice. Be guided with the following scale.

Verbal Description	Scale	Explanation
5- Strongly Agree (SA)	(4.21-5.00)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder's 81% - 100% of the time.
4- Agree (A)	(3.41 - 4.20)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder's 61% - 80% of the time.
3- Moderately Agree (MA)	(2.61 - 3.40)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder's 41% - 60% of the time.
2- Disagree (D)	(1.81 - 2.60)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder's 21% - 40% of the time.
1- Strongly Disagree (SD)	(1.00 - 1.80)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder's 1% - 20% of the time.

<i>Knowledge</i>	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Mode-rately Agree (3)	Dis-agree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. Inclusive education is a placement of all students including children with disabilities in mainstream classrooms with the necessary support given within these classrooms.					
2. Inclusive education is when an educational environment is given the same level of scrutiny as the child in order to assess the adaptations needed to achieve a more effective match between the child's educational needs and the instruction offered.					
3. Inclusive education is an approach which aims to develop a child-focus within schools by acknowledging that all children are individuals with different learning needs and speeds.					
4. Inclusive education is considered to be a means of providing educational opportunities for all children, including children with disabilities.					
5. Inclusive education is a way of reducing social discrimination.					
6. Inclusive education works as a catalyst for change because it does not only enhance education within schools, but also represents an increased awareness of human rights and leads to a reduction in social discrimination.					
7. Inclusive education enhances social interaction and inclusion among students and reduces negative stereotypes towards children with special needs.					
8. Inclusive education is seen as a system which caters for the needs of a diverse range of learners and supports diversity, effectively eliminating all forms of discrimination.					
9. Inclusion has the potential to be a very effective starting point for addressing the Rights of the Child in a range of cultures and contexts.					
10. Inclusive education is a development keeping children with disabilities in mainstream education settings rather than referring them to special schools.					
11. Inclusive education is defined as the education of children with disabilities with their non-disabled peers to the maximum extent appropriate.					
12. In an inclusive education system, school and school practices were developed to support a diverse range of learners in mainstream settings which made schools more flexible and child-centered.					

Part III
Direction:

1. Read each statement. Please respond as truthfully as you can.
2. Place a check mark (✓) on the column of your choice. Be guided with the following scale.

<i>Attitude</i>	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Moderately Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
<i>A. Cognitive (beliefs)</i>					
1. I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.					
2. I believe that students with a disability can be taught in regular classroom setting.					
3. I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior among all students.					
4. I believe that all students can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.					
5. I believe that students with a disability should be segregated because it is too expensive to modify the physical environment of the school.					
6. I believe that students with a disability should be in special education schools so that they do not experience rejection in the regular school.					
<i>B. Affective (feelings)</i>					
1. I am pleased when my teachers are able to understand students with a disability.					
2. I am happy when student with a disability can keep up with the day-to-day activity.					
3. I am contented when my teachers reported that they can communicate well with students with a disability.					
4. I am comfortable including students with a disability in a regular classroom with other students without a disability.					
5. I am glad that students with a disability are included in the regular classroom, regardless of the different disabilities.					
6. I am happy to tell my teachers to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students.					
<i>C. Behavioral (actions)</i>					
1. I am willing to encourage students with a disability to participate in all social activities in the regular classroom.					
2. I am willing to support learners with special needs through preparing the physical infrastructure and instructional resources with the collaboration from community and the MOOE.					
3. I am willing to physically include students with a disability in the regular classroom with the necessary support.					
4. I am willing to modify the physical environment to include students with a disability in the regular classroom.					
5. I am willing to send my teachers on training in teaching students with special needs					
6. I am willing to adapt the assessment of individual students in order for the inclusive education to take place.					

Questionnaire (for teachers)

Internal Stakeholders’ Knowledge and Attitude towards Inclusive Education

This questionnaire aims to identify internal stakeholders’ knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. Kindly and honestly answer the following questions. It is assured that the information you share is confidential. Thank you very much for your time and cooperation.

Part I:

School: _____

- Educational Attainment: Bachelor’s Degree
 With MA units
 Master’s Degree
 With EDD/PhD Units
 Doctor’s Degree

Years of Teaching Experience: _____ years

Year/Years of Experience in Teaching Students with Disabilities in the Classroom: _____ years

Part II:

- Direction:
 1. Read each statement. Please respond as truthfully as you can.
 2. Place a check mark (v) on the column of your choice. Be guided with the following scale.

Verbal Description	Scale	Explanation
5- Strongly Agree (SA)	(4.21-5.00)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 81% - 100% of the time.
4- Agree (A)	(3.41 – 4.20)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 61% - 80% of the time.
3- Moderately Agree (MA)	(2.61 – 3.40)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 41% - 60% of the time.
2- Disagree (D)	(1.81 – 2.60)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 21% - 40% of the time.
1- Strongly Disagree (SD)	(1.00 – 1.80)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 1% - 20% of the time.

<i>Knowledge</i>	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Moderately Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. Inclusive education is a placement of all students including children with disabilities in mainstream classrooms with the necessary support given within these classrooms.					
2. Inclusive education is when an educational environment is given the same level of scrutiny as the child in order to assess the adaptations needed to achieve a more effective match between the child's educational needs and the instruction offered.					
3. Inclusive education is an approach which aims to develop a child-focus within schools by acknowledging that all children are individuals with different learning needs and speeds.					
4. Inclusive education is considered to be a means of providing educational opportunities for all children, including children with disabilities.					
5. Inclusive education is a way of reducing social discrimination.					
6. Inclusive education works as a catalyst for change because it does not only enhances education within schools, but also represents an increased awareness of human rights and leads to a reduction in social discrimination.					
7. Inclusive education enhances social interaction and inclusion among students and reduces negative stereotypes towards children with special needs.					
8. Inclusive education is seen as a system which caters for the needs of a diverse range of learners and supports diversity, effectively eliminating all forms of discrimination.					
9. Inclusion has the potential to be a very effective starting point for addressing the Rights of the Child in a range of cultures and contexts.					
10. Inclusive education is a development keeping children with disabilities in mainstream education settings rather than referring them to special schools.					
11. Inclusive education is defined as the education of children with disabilities with their non-disabled peers to the maximum extent appropriate.					
12. In an inclusive education system, school and school practices were developed to support a diverse range of learners in mainstream settings which made schools more flexible and child-centered.					

Part III

Direction:

1. Read each statement. Please respond as truthfully as you can.
2. Place a check mark (✓) on the column of your choice. Be guided with the following scale.

<i>Attitude</i>	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Moderately Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
<i>A. Cognitive(beliefs)</i>					
1. I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.					
2. I believe that students with adisability can be taught in regular classroom setting.					
3. I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriately behavior among all students					
4. I believe that all students can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.					
5. I believe that students with a disability should be segregated because it is too expensive to modify the physical environment of the school					
6. I believe that students with a disability should be in special education schools so that they do not experience rejection in the regular school.					
<i>B. Affective (feelings)</i>					
1. I am contented when I can communicate well to students with a disability.					
2. I am happy when student with a disability can keep up with the day-to-day activity in my classroom.					
3. I am pleased when I am able to understand students with a disability.					
4. I am comfortable including students with a disability in a regular classroom with other students without a disability.					
5. I am happy that students with adisability are included in the regular classroom, regardless of the severity of the disability.					
6. I am agreeable to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students.					
<i>C. Behavioral (actions)</i>					
1. I am willing to encourage students with a disability to participate in all social activities in the regular classroom.					
2. I am willing to adapt the curriculum to meet the individual needs of all students regardless of their disability.					
3. I am willing to physically include students with a severe disability in the regular classroom with the necessary support.					
4. I am willing to modify the physical environment to include students with a disability in the regular classroom.					
5. I am willing to adapt my communication techniques to ensure that all students with an emotional and behavioral disorder can be successfully included in the regular classroom.					
6. I am willing to adapt the assessment of individual students in order for the inclusive education to take place.					

Questionnaire (for students)

Internal Stakeholders’ Knowledge and Attitude towards Inclusive Education

This questionnaire aims to identify internal stakeholders’ knowledge and attitude towards inclusive education. Kindly and honestly answer the following questions. It is assured that the information you share is confidential. Thank you very much for your time and cooperation.

Part I:

Name: _____ School: _____

Gender: Male Female

Part II:

Direction: 1. Read each statement. Please respond as truthfully as you can.
 2. Place a check mark (✓) on the column of your choice. Be guided with the following scale.

Verbal Description	Scale	Explanation
5- Strongly Agree (SA)	(4.21-5.00)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 81% - 100% of the time.
4- Agree (A)	(3.41 – 4.20)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 61% - 80% of the time.
3- Moderately Agree (MA)	(2.61 – 3.40)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 41% - 60% of the time.
2- Disagree (D)	(1.81 – 2.60)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 21% - 40% of the time.
1- Strongly Disagree (SD)	(1.00 – 1.80)	The feeling/behavior is felt/manifested by the internal stakeholder’s 1% - 20% of the time.

<i>Knowledge</i>	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Moderately Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1. Inclusive education is a placement of all students including children with disabilities in mainstream classrooms with the necessary support given within these classrooms.					
2. Inclusive education is when an educational environment is given the same level of scrutiny as the child in order to assess the adaptations needed to achieve a more effective match between the child's educational needs and the instruction offered.					
3. Inclusive education is an approach which aims to develop a child-focus within schools by acknowledging that all children are individuals with different learning needs and speeds.					
4. Inclusive education is considered to be a means of providing educational opportunities for all children, including children with disabilities.					
5. Inclusive education is a way of reducing social discrimination.					
6. Inclusive education works as a catalyst for change because it does not only enhances education within schools, but also represents an increased awareness of human rights and leads to a reduction in social discrimination.					
7. Inclusive education enhances social interaction and inclusion among students and reduces negative stereotypes towards children with special needs.					
8. Inclusive education is seen as a system which caters for the needs of a diverse range of learners and supports diversity, effectively eliminating all forms of discrimination.					
9. Inclusion has the potential to be a very effective starting point for addressing the Rights of the Child in a range of cultures and contexts.					
10. Inclusive education is a development keeping children with disabilities in mainstream education settings rather than referring them to special schools.					
11. Inclusive education is defined as the education of children with disabilities with their non-disabled peers to the maximum extent appropriate.					
12. In an inclusive education system, school and school practices were developed to support a diverse range of learners in mainstream settings which made schools more flexible and child-centered.					

Part III

Direction:

1. Read each statement. Please respond as truthfully as you can.
2. Place a check mark (✓) on the column of your choice. Be guided with the following scale.

<i>Attitude</i>	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Moderately Agree (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
<i>A. Cognitive (beliefs)</i>					
1. I believe that an inclusive school is one that permits academic progression of all students regardless of their ability.					
2. I believe that students with a disability should be taught in a regular classroom setting.					
3. I believe that inclusion facilitates socially appropriate behavior among all students.					
4. I believe that all students can learn in the regular curriculum of the school if the curriculum is adapted to meet their individual needs.					
5. I believe that students with a disability should be included with other students in a regular class.					
6. I believe that students with a disability should not be in special education schools so that they can experience acceptance in the regular school.					
<i>B. Affective (feelings)</i>					
1. I am contented when I can communicate well with my classmates with a disability.					
2. I am happy when my classmate with a disability can keep up with the day-to-day activities in our classroom.					
3. I am pleased when I am able to understand my classmate with a disability.					
4. I am comfortable if I have a classmate with a disability.					
5. I am glad that my classmates with a disability are included in the regular classroom.					
<i>C. Behavioral (actions)</i>					
1. I will encourage my classmate with a disability to participate in all classroom activities.					
2. I will help my classmate with a disability in academic areas if the need arises with the necessary support.					
3. I will help to modify the physical classroom environment to accommodate the needs of my classmate with a disability.					
4. I will use communication techniques which can be easily understood by my classmates with a disability in the classroom.					

